

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Abundance of pests of flood recession maize (*Zea mays* L.) in the Senegal River Valley

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GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2023, 23(02), 006–019

Publication history: Received on 05 March 2023; revised on 18 April 2023; accepted on 21 April 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2023.23.2.0159>

Abstract

Maize, a foodstuff of economic and nutritional importance, is grown in Senegal in four regions such as the Senegal River valley, especially in the cold season. However, maize is subject to many pests. In view of the damage they cause, a knowledge of the entomofauna remains interesting. The abundance of the entomofauna of floodplain maize in the river valley, particularly in Dembanané, was determined. Thus, a population of 590 individuals was collected. Consequently, the absolute and relative abundance and frequency of occurrence or Constance were evaluated. The Kruskal-wallis test was performed followed by the DUNN test. Following this a Fisher test and a Chi-2 test were performed. From the beginning of flowering to the beginning of ripening, the study covered 58 species of insects and 5 species of spiders belonging to eight orders. The absolute abundance of species varies according to the plot and the development phase. In addition, Heteroptera are the most represented with 35.46% followed by Coleoptera and Orthoptera with 26.24%. The contribution of each species in this study area differs as a result of the different values found of relative abundance and Constance.

Keywords: Abundance; Bio-pest; flood recession maize; Parasitoid; Senegal River Valley

1. Introduction

Global cereal production is dominated by three cereals [1], including maize, which ranks first ahead of wheat and rice [2]. Introduced to Africa by Portuguese explorers around the 16th century [3], maize (*Zea mays* L.) represents a staple food for many African countries [4]. In Senegal, this cereal is mainly grown for its grain in four regions: eastern Senegal, Sine-Saloum, Casamance, and the Senegal River Valley. However, according to statistics from the Directorate Général for Agricultural Protection (DGAP), maize production in the valley does not exceed 10% of the national total [3]. Thus, due to climatic changes in this environment, farmers generally grow maize in a rotation system with legumes [5] during the flood season to ensure a low but secure yield [6].

In fact, despite its importance for food and industry, the corn plant is often subject to numerous pests, of which insects are the most distinguished. In addition to the climatic factors limiting the production of corn, the intensification of irrigated agriculture has favored a pullulation of pests causing several losses to the corn in culture. These pests belong to lepidopterans, coleopterans, hemipterans and orthopterans. Of course, all parts of the plant are susceptible to attack, but the most noted pests are associated with roots, stalk, cobs and kernels [7]. As a result, damage occurs, disrupting plant development, reducing yields, and rendering the ear unsuitable for the market.

In response to these constraints related to insect attacks, a research project on irrigated maize production in the Senegal River region was initiated in the early 1990s. In addition, Goebel [8], proposed an overview of the main entomological

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constraints encountered in the Senegal River region and to review the various control options in the new context of irrigated cropping systems. More recently, a census of the entomofauna frequenting sweet corn was made by Mbow [9].

Therefore, a better knowledge of the entomofauna of floodplain maize in the river valley would allow us to contribute to the improvement of floodplain maize crop protection. The general objective of this study is to evaluate the abundance of maize pests and their possible natural enemies in order to find means of control to ensure the maintenance of a rate that is below economically acceptable thresholds. Thus, it is specifically to :

- Determine absolute abundance,
- Assess relative abundance,
- Determine the frequency of occurrence of species.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study framework

Dembancané is a commune since 2008 in the department of Kanel of the region of Matam. Its coordinates are 15° 05 north and 12° 42 west with an altitude of 23m. It is located near the Senegal River and the border with Mauritania and is crossed by the N2 national road that links Bakel and Matam. According to the eco-geographical zones of Matam, it is located in the locality of Walo, otherwise known as "Dande mayo", a flood zone par excellence characterized by flood recession and irrigated cultivation (corn, sweet potato, sorghum...). These crops, intended for self-consumption, use local varieties. Maize in this area is often rotated with cowpeas and sweet potatoes.

Being an agro-ecological zone, Dembancané is marked by a vegetation dominated by *Acacia nilotica* but also presents *Balanites aegyptiaca*, *Piliostigma reticulatum*, *Momordica charantia*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Gossypium* sp... It responds to the needs of the production and supply of agricultural and fisheries products [10].

Figure 1 Geographical map of Dembancané

2.2. Sampling, Collection and Breeding of species

For this study, seven fields considered as plots were randomly selected from this area. The first five have a perimeter of 45m wide and 400m long, the sixth has a width of 50m by 400m long and the seventh has a width of 50m by 500m long. The survey was conducted from December 25, 2020. Out of seven partials, sampling was conducted at dusk in a random

fashion. Although the maize plant has three developmental phases, our research focused on the last two particularly at the early flowering and early maturation stages present in the field.

The collection was carried out during 7 days. Thus, insects were taken directly from the plant with insect forceps or captured in the surrounding area with a net. Indeed, these species were trapped because they are generally found in the seedling's cones. However, others to count spiders were found on the leaves, the folds of the leaves, in the spike and on the stem.

Figure 2 Types of traps used (A) the net and (B) the pincer at dusk (C)

Then, they were put in labeled tubes containing 70° alcohol to avoid putrefaction. In addition, the rearing of the collected larvae was started, providing them with corn leaves (Figure 3a) to continue their development cycle (Figure 3b).

Figure 3 Insect rearing (a=larva, b= pupa)

2.3. Identification of the species encountered

The identification of these species was carried out thanks to the collection of the IFAN (Institut Fondamental d'Afrique Noire). Indeed, their morphological recognition is carried out with the help of magnifying glass by comparing their morphological characteristics with those of the collection. The collected species are distributed and classified taxonomically.

Figure 4 Morphological recognition of collected species

2.4. Abundance

2.4.1. Absolute abundance

Absolute abundance (Aa) is the total number of individuals caught of a species [11].

2.4.2. Relative frequency or relative abundance

Relative frequency (f) is the percentage of individuals of a species relative to the total number of individuals of all species [12].

$$f = ni \cdot 100 / N \quad \text{or} \quad Ar \% = Aa \cdot 100 / At$$

ni : Number of individuals of a given species

N : Total number of individuals of all species combined

According to Faurie *et al.* [11], relative abundance values are ranked at several levels:

If $Ar\% < 5\%$ then the species is very rare

If $5\% < Ar\% < 25\%$ the species is rare

If $25\% < Ar\% < 50\%$ the species is common

If $50\% < Ar\% < 75\%$ the species is abundant

If $Ar\% > 75\%$ the species is very abundant

2.5. Frequency of occurrence or Consistency

Frequency of occurrence is the ratio of the number of surveys where species i occurs to the total number of surveys multiplied by one hundred [9].

$$Fo\% = Pi \cdot 100 / P$$

Pi : number of surveys where species i is present

P : total number of surveys

According to Dajoy, based on Fo values, we have several categories of species:

Rare species if $Fo < 5\%$

Accidental species if $5\% < F_o < 25\%$.
 Accessory species if $25\% < F_o < 50\%$.
 Regular species if $50\% < F_o < 75\%$.
 Constant species if $75\% < F_o < 100$
 Ubiquitous species if $F_o = 100\%$ [11].

2.6. Statistical analysis

Data analysis was conducted using Excel and Python version 3.8 from Python Software Foundation [13] for graphing and R studio version 4.0.3 from R Core Team [14] for statistical testing. The Kruskal-wallis test (non-parametric) is performed for a multiple comparison of the mean ranks of the corresponding variable. Thus, each mean is assigned to a letter. According to the statistics, means assigned to the same letters or having at least one letter in common do not differ significantly. However, two averages differ if they have no letters in common. Dunn's test is performed to test the significance of the mean ranks per pair of plots. A Fisher test is performed to test if the distribution of the orders of the collected species is distinct or not. In addition, the Chi-2 test of independence is performed to test the linkage of certain species.

3. Results

3.1. Inventory of species encountered

A total of 585 insects and 5 spiders belonging to eight orders were collected in the Dembanané site. The Fisher test gives a p-value of 1. The insects consisted of 58 species distributed in 24 families and 7 orders (Heteroptera, Coleoptera, Orthoptera, Homoptera, Thysanoptera, Lepidoptera, Neuroptera). On the other hand, spiders are composed of five (5) species belonging to the order Araneae.

3.2. Abundance of species encountered

Heteroptera are the most abundant with 35.46%, followed by Coleoptera and Orthoptera with 26.24%. In contrast to these orders, Homoptera, Thysanoptera, Lepidoptera, Araneae and Neuroptera are the least represented (Figure 5).

The absolute abundance of species by plot (A to G) is shown in Figure 6. Thus, it varies according to the plot and the phase of development of the corn.

The analysis in Table 1 shows a comparison of the mean of the species of the different plots in a two-to-one way following the Kruskal-wallis test. Thus, the significance of the differences is shown by Dunn's test.

The relative abundance of these species is shown in Figure 7. We have one common species (*Piezodorus* sp.), five rare species (*Rhaphidopalpa* sp., *Eysarcoris inconspicuus*, *Geocoris amabilis*, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, and *Pyrgomorpha cognata*), and very rare species.

The calculation of the constancy of these species shows that some species are accidental. This is the case of *Caryedon serratus*, others are accessory (*Naphius* sp., *Paederus* sp., *Tribolium castaneum* and *Spermophagus* sp.). Thus the group of other species consists of regular, constant and ubiquitous species (Figure 8). Only one species (*Anthicus* sp.) is constant with $F_o = 85, 71\%$. Four are found regular including *Rhaphidopalpa* sp., *Thrips* sp., *Calidea nana* and *Leptocoris* sp. Five species are omnipresent: *E. inconspicuus*, *Dimorphopterus* sp., *G. amabilis*, *Piezodorus* sp., *P. cognata* and *Oecanthus pellucens* with a frequency of 100%. Thus, following a Chi-2 test of independence, the P-value found is 0.99, greater than 0.05.

Figure 5 Percentages of the different insect orders and the spider order

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

Figure 6 Absolute abundance of species by plot (A to G) at early flowering and early ripening stages

Table 1 Average species on the different plots

Stage1								
		Plot A	Plot B	Plot C	Plot D	Plot E	Plot F	Plot G
	Mean	0.722 ^a	0.586 ^a	0.312 ^a	1.24 ^b	1.789 ^{ab}	0	0
	Standard error	0.321	0.144	0.119	0.29	0.735	0	0
Stage2								
		Plot A	Plot B	Plot C	Plot D	Plot E	Plot F	Plot G
	Mean	3.333 ^{ab}	2.517 ^a	2.812 ^b	2.76 ^a	3 ^{ab}	4.4 ^b	7.534 ^b
	Standard error	1.323	0.891	0.764	1.242	0.837	1.489	2.914

Values are means followed by standard deviation. Means assigned to the same letters or having at least one letter in common have no significant differences. However, two averages differ if they have no common letter

Figure 7 Relative abundance of species in the study area

Trichogramma are not encountered at either stage. The absence of these species could lead to the abundant presence of this pest in all plots.

Spodoptera frugiperda is rare in the area except for plot G where it is abundant. This unevenness in its distribution could be explained by the fact that it is an invasive species. Indeed, it was first introduced in Africa in 2016 [20]. However, Djidjonri *et al.* [16] found *Spodoptera frugiperda* to be the most represented in Cameroon.

Helicoverpa armigera, which is very rare in this environment, belongs to the order Lepidoptera and has a wide host range that allows it to expand geographically. This pest causes severe damage along its range on maize, cotton, tomato and even vegetable crops [21]. Its rarity could be explained by the intercropping of cowpea, sweet potato in the study area. Thus, according to EPPO [21], its impact could be reduced to an economic threshold through crop rotation. But also, *H. armigera* has a lower fecundity rate on maize compared to cowpea. Indeed, it seems that maize possesses enzyme inhibitors acting on the digestion of the larvae of this pest [22]. Indeed, this commodity contains molecules capable of acting on certain natural enemies [7]. For example, studies have shown that 2,4-dihydroxy-7-methoxy-1,4-benzoxazin-3-one (DIMBOA) is an inhibitor that causes a reduction in the digestion capacity of *H. armigera* larvae, while 6-methoxybenzoxazolinin-3-one (MBOA) reduces the conversion efficiency of digested food [23].

Through the frequency of occurrence values, species are found incidental in this area in the case of *Caryedon serratus* (the peanut bruchid), *Cheilomenes sulphurea*, *Scymnus senegalensis* and *Exochomus foudrasi*. Indeed, the presence of *C. serratus* would be due to the existence of its host plant *Piliostigma reticulatum* [24] found around the plots. However, ladybugs would be present in this area due to the existence of *Gossipium* sp. near the plots. According to Miranda *et al.* [25], these small ladybugs are numerous in cotton crops.

Accessory species are encountered (*Naphius* sp., *Paederus* sp., *Tribolium castaneum* and *Spermophagus* sp.). Of these, *Spermophagus* sp. represents a primary stock pest. However, its presence could be explained by the fact that its infestation starts in the field. Indeed, it belongs to the bruchidae family. These bruchids mainly attack legumes but they are also associated with the convolvulaceae family [26] such as sweet potato in this area.

Anthicus sp. the only constant species in the environment, is a predator of *Thrips* [27]. Thus, its presence could be justified by the regularity of its prey. *Thrips* sp. attacks both cowpea [28] and the maize plant, which becomes dry, stunted, yellowed and its deformed leaves curl up on itself [29].

Then, *Rhaphidopalpa* sp. is found regular in the environment. Indeed, *Rhaphidopalpa* sp. is a pest of Cucurbitaceae. However, corn is often put for trap in these crops knowing that it is a resting medium for this species [30]. Therefore, its presence would be due to the existence of *Momordica charantia* and the impact of corn on its ecology.

Finally, six species are omnipresent. This is because all these species namely *Eysarcoris inconspicuus*, *Dimorphopterus* sp., *G. amabilis*, *Piezodorus* sp., *Pyrgomorpha cognata* and *Oecanthus pellucens* are present in all surveys. Thus, these obtained results disagree with those of Mbow [9] where only one species was found ubiquitous. These species are found unrelated with a significant P-value equal to 0.99. This could be explained by the fact that some are generalist predators and others are phytophagous. The genus *Oecanthus* are predators of insects, particularly soft-bodied insects [31].

The different abundance and constancy values show the importance of each species in the environment. However, a species in abundance or a species represented by a single individual does not make the same contribution to the ecosystem [9].

5. Conclusion

This study focuses on the entomofauna of flood recession maize in the Senegal River valley, consisting of 590 individuals, including 585 insects and 5 spiders, divided into eight orders (Heteroptera, Coleoptera, Orthoptera, Homoptera, Thysanoptera, Lepidoptera, Neuroptera and Araneae). Thus, their absolute abundance varies according to the plot and the development phase of the corn. Despite the different values of relative abundance and Constance of species, Heteroptera are the most represented.

Additional studies are needed to better understand the entomofauna of maize. Thus, it would be interesting to broaden the sampling on the different phases of development of flood recession maize, to extend our research to other study stations but also to broaden this work by extending our studies to other crops, namely rice, millet, and sorghum.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors thank all those who participated in the success of this research article.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest of this research work.

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